

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

Coordinator Approval Cover Sheet

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XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D3.5

Performance Assessment

 <https://xrotor-project.eu>

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
1 Introduction	5
2 Overview of the X-Rotor simulation model	6
2.1 Control and Filtering	7
2.2 Selected Operating Points	7
3 Performance Assessment at Below Rated Operation	8
3.1 Mode 1	8
3.2 Mode 2	16
3.3 Mode 3	38
4 Above Rated Operation	46
4.1 Mode 4	46
4.2 Mode 5	62
Bibliography	78

List of Tables

1 X-Rotor operating points 7

About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO2 emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects. If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable reports on the performance of the X-rotor wind turbine when controlled as described in Deliverable D3.4. The controller caters for the full operation envelop of the wind turbine including both below and above rated wind speed. Representative results are provided at ambient wind speeds for each mode, below rated constant secondary rotor speed, $C_{P_{max}}$ tracking by both primary and secondary rotor, transition from below rated to above rated, above rated constant primary rotor torque and above rated constant primary rotor power.

1 Introduction

The X-rotor operational strategy is discussed in D3.1 (1) and the design of the controller in D3.4 (2) control related models. As reported in (1), three options for the operating strategy of secondary rotors have been considered, namely, for a given ambient wind speed,

- i their rotational speed is held constant; that is, it does not vary with primary rotor azimuthal angle
- ii their tip speed ratio is constant; that is, it does not vary with primary rotor azimuthal angle
- iii the rotational speed of both secondary rotors is the same with the tip speed ratio of the secondary rotor, when rotating into the ambient wind speed, held constant.

Option (iii) is preferred and the design of its controller is described in D3.4 (2). The controller has 5 modes, namely,

1. Mode 1: below rated constant secondary rotor speed.
2. Mode 2: below rated CPmax tracking by both primary and secondary rotor.
3. Mode 3: pre-emptive pitching transition from below rated to above rated.
4. Mode 5: above rated constant primary rotor torque.
5. Mode 5: above rated constant primary rotor power.

However, two minor amendments are made in the work described here in comparison to D3.4. First, in Mode 1, the secondary rotor speed is held constant rather than the tip speed ratio of the secondary rotor rotating into the ambient wind. Second, in Modes 2, 3, 4 and 5, the target tip speed ratios for the secondary rotor, when rotating into the ambient wind speed, is held constant at its optimal value. The target tip speed ratio is not always achievable in Mode 5 due to constraints on the maximum secondary rotor speed. Accordingly, an upper limit is placed on secondary rotor tip speed ratio. The control design models, described in Deliverable D3.3 (3), are used when designing the controller in D3.4. In this report, Deliverable D3.5 Performance assessment, an overview of the controlled wind turbine's performance is provided through a set of simulation results covering the whole operational envelope. The set consists of simulations for the following mean wind speeds.

1. Mode 1: mean wind speed at the midpoint of its range, i.e. 4m/s.
2. Mode 2: mean wind speeds at 7, 8 and 9m/s.
3. Mode 3: mean wind speed at the midpoint of its range, i.e. 11.5m/s.
4. Mode 4: mean wind speeds at 14 and 17m/s.
5. Mode 5: mean wind speeds at 20 and 23m/s.

As turbulence intensity tends to decrease as mean wind speed increases, the turbulence intensity for Mode 1 and Mode 2 is chosen to be 10% and for Mode 3, Mode 4 and Mode 5 is chosen to be 6%. The simulation model, reported in Deliverable D3.3, is used to obtain time series data.

The rest of the report is organised as follows. In **section 2** an overview of the full nonlinear model with full envelope controller and the set operating points are given. In **section 3** the X-Rotor control system performance is assessed for below rated wind speed values. Above rated operation of the X-Rotor control system is assessed in **section 4**.

2 Overview of the X-Rotor simulation model

The X-Rotor simulation model with full envelope controller is represented in Figure 1, wherein subscripts P and S indicate whether variables are associated with the primary or secondary rotor variables respectively.

Figure 1: X-Rotor dynamic structure and controller

Full details of the simulation model are provided in Deliverable D3.2 (4). It includes dynamic models for the wind field, the primary rotor structural dynamics and power take-off dynamics which includes both secondary rotors and their power-trains dynamics.

The wind field model provides time varying wind speeds over the swept area to provide correctly correlated aerodynamic forces and moments up to 6P.

The primary rotor dynamics include an aerodynamic model based on using aerodynamic coefficients. It is dependent on β , the pitch angle set by the full envelope controller, and V_P , the wind speeds experienced by each blade as the primary rotor rotates through the modelled wind field. The input, T_S , is the thrust from the secondary rotors that provides the reaction torque to the primary rotor. The primary rotor model includes the first edge and flap dynamic modes for each upper and lower blade.

The power take-off includes models for each secondary rotor unit, each of which includes models of a rotor, shaft, generator and controller. The aerodynamic model for each secondary rotor is again based on aerodynamic coefficients and is dependent on V_S , the wind speed induced by the rotation of the primary rotor through the wind field. When rotating into the wind, the secondary rotors are required to operate at a specific tip speed ratio corresponding to the input, k_c . This requirement is ensured by the controller incorporated into the power take-off unit. From a control perspective, the power take-off can be interpreted as an actuator acting in response to k_c .

The controller has inputs Ω_P and ω_e , where Ω_P is the primary rotor speed and ω_e is the frequency of the power generated by the power take-off units, a surrogate for the secondary rotors'

rotational speed. It acts on these inputs to regulate operation of the turbines through its outputs, β and k_c .

2.1 Control and Filtering

The design of the full envelop controller is provided in D3.4 (2). Suitable linearised models for controller design can be found in D3.3 (3). The full envelop controller acts to regulate the secondary rotor in Mode 1 through adjusting k_c in response to a measurement of ω_e . It, also, acts to regulate the primary rotor in Modes 3 to 5, through adjusting β . In Mode 3 the regulation is open loop and in Modes 4 and 5 it is closed loop in response to a measurement of Ω_P .

The controllers in Modes 1, 4 and 5 are essentially PI controllers augmented with filters at specific lightly damped structural modes and various nP frequencies. The Mode 1 controller is tuned to achieve a crossover frequency of 0.53 rad/s with a phase margin of 88.5° and a gain margin of 38.1 dB. The Mode 4 and 5 controller is tuned to achieve a crossover frequency of 0.98 rad/s with a phase margin of 63.5°.

2.2 Selected Operating Points

Based on the operational strategy defined in Deliverable D3.1 (1), the operating points given in Table 1 are selected to illustrate the performance of the controlled X-Rotor simulation model.

Mode	V_P [m/s]	Ω_P [rad/s]	Q_P [Nm]	V_S [rad/s]	Ω_{S_c} [rad/s]	Q_S [Nm]	β [deg]	k_c [Nm s^2]
1	4	0.28	0.86E6	21	20	0.53E4	0	13.25
2	7	0.47	2.81E6	35	22.33	2.29E4	0	45.96
2	8	0.53	3.67E6	40	25.52	2.99E4	0	45.96
2	9	0.60	4.65E6	45	28.72	3.79E4	0	45.96
3	11.5	0.76	7.45E6	57	36.33	6.07E4	-4.25	45.96
4	14	0.79	8.27E6	60	38.29	6.74E4	-14.24	45.96
4	17	0.79	8.29E6	60	38.29	6.74E4	-16.69	45.96
4	20	0.79	8.22E6	60	38.29	6.74E4	-18.84	45.96
4	23	0.79	8.07E6	60	38.29	6.74E4	-20.88	45.96

Table 1: X-Rotor operating points

For each operating point, the following data is presented, both in time domain plots and spectra.

- Primary rotor. Operational strategy, aerodynamic torque vs rotor speed, wind speed, torque at the hub, rotor speed, power, pitch angle (when appropriate), upper and lower in-plane and out-of-plane root bending moments (RBM), upper and lower blade in-plane and out-of-plane angular displacement.
- Secondary rotors. Average operational strategy, aerodynamic torque vs rotor speed, incident wind speed, rotor speed, rotor torque, rotor thrust, sum of both rotors thrust and sum of rotors power.

3 Performance Assessment at Below Rated Operation

3.1 Mode 1

3.1.1 wind speed = 4m/s, incident wind speed = 20m/s

List of figures in 3.1.1

2	Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 4m/s wind speed	9
3	4m/s wind speed	9
4	4m/s wind speed PSD	9
5	Primary rotor speed at 4m/s wind speed	10
6	Primary rotor speed PSD at 4m/s wind speed	10
7	Primary rotor torque at 4m/s wind speed	10
8	Primary rotor torque PSD at 4m/s wind speed	10
9	Primary rotor power at 4m/s wind speed	10
10	Primary rotor power PSD at 4m/s wind speed	10
11	Upper blade in-plane RBM at 4m/s wind speed	11
12	Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 4m/s wind speed	11
13	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 4m/s wind speed	11
14	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 4m/s wind speed	11
15	Lower blade in-plane RBM at 4m/s wind speed	11
16	Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 4m/s wind speed	11
17	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 4m/s wind speed	12
18	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 4m/s wind speed	12
19	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 4m/s wind speed	12
20	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 4m/s wind speed	12
21	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 4m/s wind speed	12
22	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 4m/s wind speed	12
23	Variation of secondary rotor torque to variation of rotor speed at 20m/s incident wind speed (4m/s ambient wind speed)	13
24	20m/s incident wind speed	13
25	20m/s incident wind speed PSD	13
26	Secondary rotor speed at 20m/s incident wind speed	13
27	Secondary rotor speed PSD at 20m/s incident wind speed	13

28 Secondary rotor torque at 20m/s incident wind speed 14

29 Secondary rotor torque PSD at 20m/s incident wind speed 14

30 Secondary rotor thrust at 20m/s incident wind speed 14

31 Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 20m/s incident wind speed 14

32 Secondary rotors combined power at 20m/s incident wind speed 14

33 Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 20m/s incident wind speed 14

34 Secondary rotors combined thrust at 4m/s incident wind speed 15

35 Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 20m/s incident wind speed 15

Figure 2: Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 3: 4m/s wind speed

Figure 4: 4m/s wind speed PSD

Figure 5: Primary rotor speed at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 6: Primary rotor speed PSD at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 7: Primary rotor torque at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 8: Primary rotor torque PSD at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 9: Primary rotor power at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 10: Primary rotor power PSD at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 11: Upper blade in-plane RBM at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 12: Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 13: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 14: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 15: Lower blade in-plane RBM at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 16: Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 17: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 18: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 19: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 20: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 21: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 22: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 4m/s wind speed

Figure 23: Variation of secondary rotor torque to variation of rotor speed at 20m/s incident wind speed (4m/s ambient wind speed)

Figure 24: 20m/s incident wind speed

Figure 25: 20m/s incident wind speed PSD

Figure 26: Secondary rotor speed at 20m/s incident wind speed

Figure 27: Secondary rotor speed PSD at 20m/s incident wind speed

Figure 28: Secondary rotor torque at 20m/s incident wind speed

Figure 29: Secondary rotor torque PSD at 20m/s incident wind speed

Figure 30: Secondary rotor thrust at 20m/s incident wind speed

Figure 31: Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 20m/s incident wind speed

Figure 32: Secondary rotors combined power at 20m/s incident wind speed

Figure 33: Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 20m/s incident wind speed

Figure 34: Secondary rotors combined thrust at 4m/s incident wind speed

Figure 35: Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 20m/s incident wind speed

3.2 Mode 2

3.2.1 wind speed = 7m/s, incident wind speed = 35m/s

List of figures in 3.2.1

36	Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 7m/s wind speed	17
37	7m/s wind speed.....	17
38	7m/s wind speed PSD.....	17
39	Primary rotor speed at 7m/s wind speed	18
40	Primary rotor speed PSD at 7m/s wind speed	18
41	Primary rotor torque at 7m/s wind speed.....	18
42	Primary rotor torque PSD at 7m/s wind speed.....	18
43	Primary rotor power at 7m/s wind speed	18
44	Primary rotor power PSD at 7m/s wind speed	18
45	Upper blade in-plane RBM at 7m/s wind speed	19
46	Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 7m/s wind speed	19
47	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 7m/s wind speed	19
48	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 7m/s wind speed	19
49	Lower blade in-plane RBM at 7m/s wind speed	19
50	Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 7m/s wind speed	19
51	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 7m/s wind speed	20
52	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 7m/s wind speed	20
53	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 7m/s wind speed	20
54	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 7m/s wind speed	20
55	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 7m/s wind speed	20
56	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 7m/s wind speed	20
57	Variation of secondary rotor torque to variation of rotor speed at 35m/s incident wind speed (7m/s ambient wind speed)	21
58	35m/s incident wind speed.....	21
59	35m/s incident wind speed PSD.....	21
60	Secondary rotor speed at 35m/s incident wind speed	21
61	Secondary rotor speed PSD at 35m/s incident wind speed	21
62	Secondary rotor torque at 35m/s incident wind speed.....	22
63	Secondary rotor torque PSD at 35m/s incident wind speed.....	22
64	Secondary rotor thrust at 35m/s incident wind speed.....	22

65 Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 35m/s incident wind speed 22

66 Secondary rotors combined power at 35m/s incident wind speed 22

67 Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 35m/s incident wind speed 22

68 Secondary rotors combined thrust at 7m/s incident wind speed 23

69 Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 35m/s incident wind speed 23

Figure 36: Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 37: 7m/s wind speed

Figure 38: 7m/s wind speed PSD

Figure 39: Primary rotor speed at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 40: Primary rotor speed PSD at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 41: Primary rotor torque at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 42: Primary rotor torque PSD at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 43: Primary rotor power at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 44: Primary rotor power PSD at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 45: Upper blade in-plane RBM at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 46: Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 47: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 48: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 49: Lower blade in-plane RBM at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 50: Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 51: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 52: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 53: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 54: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 55: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 56: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 7m/s wind speed

Figure 57: Variation of secondary rotor torque to variation of rotor speed at 35m/s incident wind speed (7m/s ambient wind speed)

Figure 58: 35m/s incident wind speed

Figure 59: 35m/s incident wind speed PSD

Figure 60: Secondary rotor speed at 35m/s incident wind speed

Figure 61: Secondary rotor speed PSD at 35m/s incident wind speed

Figure 62: Secondary rotor torque at 35m/s incident wind speed

Figure 63: Secondary rotor torque PSD at 35m/s incident wind speed

Figure 64: Secondary rotor thrust at 35m/s incident wind speed

Figure 65: Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 35m/s incident wind speed

Figure 66: Secondary rotors combined power at 35m/s incident wind speed

Figure 67: Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 35m/s incident wind speed

Figure 68: Secondary rotors combined thrust at 7m/s incident wind speed

Figure 69: Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 35m/s incident wind speed

3.2.2 wind speed = 8m/s, incident wind speed = 40m/s

List of figures in 3.2.2

70	Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 8m/s wind speed	25
71	8m/s wind speed.....	25
72	8m/s wind speed PSD.....	25
73	Primary rotor speed at 8m/s wind speed	25
74	Primary rotor speed PSD at 8m/s wind speed	25
75	Primary rotor torque at 8m/s wind speed.....	26
76	Primary rotor torque PSD at 8m/s wind speed.....	26
77	Primary rotor power at 8m/s wind speed	26
78	Primary rotor power PSD at 8m/s wind speed	26
79	Upper blade in-plane RBM at 8m/s wind speed	26
80	Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 8m/s wind speed	26
81	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 8m/s wind speed	27
82	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 8m/s wind speed	27
83	Lower blade in-plane RBM at 8m/s wind speed	27
84	Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 8m/s wind speed	27
85	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 8m/s wind speed	27
86	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 8m/s wind speed	27
87	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 8m/s wind speed	28
88	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 8m/s wind speed	28
89	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 8m/s wind speed	28
90	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 8m/s wind speed	28
91	Variation of secondary rotor torque to variation of rotor speed at 40m/s incident wind speed (8m/s ambient wind speed)	28
92	40m/s incident wind speed.....	29
93	40m/s incident wind speed PSD.....	29
94	Secondary rotor speed at 40m/s incident wind speed	29
95	Secondary rotor speed PSD at 40m/s incident wind speed	29
96	Secondary rotor torque at 40m/s incident wind speed.....	29
97	Secondary rotor torque PSD at 40m/s incident wind speed.....	29
98	Secondary rotor thrust at 40m/s incident wind speed.....	30
99	Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 40m/s incident wind speed.....	30

100 Secondary rotors combined power at 40m/s incident wind speed 30

101 Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 40m/s incident wind speed 30

102 Secondary rotors combined thrust at 8m/s incident wind speed 30

103 Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 40m/s incident wind speed 30

Figure 70: Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 71: 8m/s wind speed

Figure 72: 8m/s wind speed PSD

Figure 73: Primary rotor speed at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 74: Primary rotor speed PSD at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 75: Primary rotor torque at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 76: Primary rotor torque PSD at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 77: Primary rotor power at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 78: Primary rotor power PSD at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 79: Upper blade in-plane RBM at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 80: Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 81: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 82: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 83: Lower blade in-plane RBM at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 84: Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 85: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 86: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 87: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 88: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 89: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 90: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 8m/s wind speed

Figure 91: Variation of secondary rotor torque to variation of rotor speed at 40m/s incident wind speed (8m/s ambient wind speed)

Figure 92: 40m/s incident wind speed

Figure 93: 40m/s incident wind speed PSD

Figure 94: Secondary rotor speed at 40m/s incident wind speed

Figure 95: Secondary rotor speed PSD at 40m/s incident wind speed

Figure 96: Secondary rotor torque at 40m/s incident wind speed

Figure 97: Secondary rotor torque PSD at 40m/s incident wind speed

Figure 98: Secondary rotor thrust at 40m/s incident wind speed

Figure 99: Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 40m/s incident wind speed

Figure 100: Secondary rotors combined power at 40m/s incident wind speed

Figure 101: Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 40m/s incident wind speed

Figure 102: Secondary rotors combined thrust at 8m/s incident wind speed

Figure 103: Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 40m/s incident wind speed

3.2.3 wind speed = 9m/s, incident wind speed = 45m/s

List of figures in 3.2.3

104	Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 9m/s wind speed	32
105	9m/s wind speed.....	32
106	9m/s wind speed PSD.....	32
107	Primary rotor speed at 9m/s wind speed	32
108	Primary rotor speed PSD at 9m/s wind speed	32
109	Primary rotor torque at 9m/s wind speed.....	33
110	Primary rotor torque PSD at 9m/s wind speed.....	33
111	Primary rotor power at 9m/s wind speed	33
112	Primary rotor power PSD at 9m/s wind speed	33
113	Upper blade in-plane RBM at 9m/s wind speed	33
114	Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 9m/s wind speed	33
115	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 9m/s wind speed	34
116	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 9m/s wind speed	34
117	Lower blade in-plane RBM at 9m/s wind speed	34
118	Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 9m/s wind speed	34
119	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 9m/s wind speed	34
120	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 9m/s wind speed	34
121	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 9m/s wind speed	35
122	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 9m/s wind speed	35
123	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 9m/s wind speed	35
124	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 9m/s wind speed	35
125	Variation of secondary rotor torque to variation of rotor speed at 45m/s incident wind speed (9m/s ambient wind speed)	35
126	45m/s incident wind speed.....	36
127	45m/s incident wind speed PSD.....	36
128	Secondary rotor speed at 45m/s incident wind speed	36
129	Secondary rotor speed PSD at 45m/s incident wind speed	36
130	Secondary rotor torque at 45m/s incident wind speed.....	36
131	Secondary rotor torque PSD at 45m/s incident wind speed.....	36
132	Secondary rotor thrust at 45m/s incident wind speed.....	37
133	Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 45m/s incident wind speed.....	37

134 Secondary rotors combined power at 45m/s incident wind speed 37
 135 Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 45m/s incident wind speed 37
 136 Secondary rotors combined thrust at 9m/s incident wind speed 37
 137 Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 45m/s incident wind speed 37

Figure 104: Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 105: 9m/s wind speed

Figure 106: 9m/s wind speed PSD

Figure 107: Primary rotor speed at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 108: Primary rotor speed PSD at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 109: Primary rotor torque at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 110: Primary rotor torque PSD at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 111: Primary rotor power at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 112: Primary rotor power PSD at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 113: Upper blade in-plane RBM at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 114: Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 115: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 116: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 117: Lower blade in-plane RBM at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 118: Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 119: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 120: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 121: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 122: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 123: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 124: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 9m/s wind speed

Figure 125: Variation of secondary rotor torque to variation of rotor speed at 45m/s incident wind speed (9m/s ambient wind speed)

Figure 126: 45m/s incident wind speed

Figure 127: 45m/s incident wind speed PSD

Figure 128: Secondary rotor speed at 45m/s incident wind speed

Figure 129: Secondary rotor speed PSD at 45m/s incident wind speed

Figure 130: Secondary rotor torque at 45m/s incident wind speed

Figure 131: Secondary rotor torque PSD at 45m/s incident wind speed

Figure 132: Secondary rotor thrust at 45m/s incident wind speed

Figure 133: Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 45m/s incident wind speed

Figure 134: Secondary rotors combined power at 45m/s incident wind speed

Figure 135: Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 45m/s incident wind speed

Figure 136: Secondary rotors combined thrust at 9m/s incident wind speed

Figure 137: Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 45m/s incident wind speed

3.3 Mode 3

3.3.1 wind speed = 11.5m/s, incident wind speed = 57m/s

List of figures in 3.3.1

138	Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 11.5m/s wind speed.....	39
139	11.5m/s wind speed	39
140	11.5m/s wind speed PSD	39
141	Primary rotor speed at 11.5m/s wind speed.....	40
142	Primary rotor speed PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed.....	40
143	Primary rotor torque at 11.5m/s wind speed	40
144	Primary rotor torque PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed	40
145	Primary rotor power at 11.5m/s wind speed.....	40
146	Primary rotor power PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed.....	40
147	Primary rotor pitch angle at 11.5m/s wind speed	41
148	Primary rotor pitch angle PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed	41
149	Upper blade in-plane RBM at 11.5m/s wind speed	41
150	Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed	41
151	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 11.5m/s wind speed.....	41
152	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed.....	41
153	Lower blade in-plane RBM at 11.5m/s wind speed	42
154	Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed	42
155	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 11.5m/s wind speed	42
156	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed	42
157	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 11.5m/s wind speed.....	42
158	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed.....	42
159	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 11.5m/s wind speed	43
160	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed	43
161	Variation of secondary rotor torque to variation of rotor speed at 57m/s incident wind speed (11.5m/s ambient wind speed)	43
162	57m/s incident wind speed.....	43
163	57m/s incident wind speed PSD.....	43
164	Secondary rotor speed at 57m/s incident wind speed	44
165	Secondary rotor speed PSD at 57m/s incident wind speed	44
166	Secondary rotor torque at 57m/s incident wind speed.....	44

167 Secondary rotor torque PSD at 57m/s incident wind speed 44

168 Secondary rotor thrust at 57m/s incident wind speed 44

169 Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 57m/s incident wind speed 44

170 Secondary rotors combined power at 57m/s incident wind speed 45

171 Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 57m/s incident wind speed 45

172 Secondary rotors combined thrust at 57m/s incident wind speed 45

173 Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 57m/s incident wind speed 45

Figure 138: Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 139: 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 140: 11.5m/s wind speed PSD

Figure 141: Primary rotor speed at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 142: Primary rotor speed PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 143: Primary rotor torque at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 144: Primary rotor torque PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 145: Primary rotor power at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 146: Primary rotor power PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 147: Primary rotor pitch angle at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 148: Primary rotor pitch angle PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 149: Upper blade in-plane RBM at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 150: Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 151: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 152: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 153: Lower blade in-plane RBM at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 154: Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 155: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 156: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 157: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 158: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 159: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 160: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 11.5m/s wind speed

Figure 161: Variation of secondary rotor torque to variation of rotor speed at 57m/s incident wind speed (11.5m/s ambient wind speed)

Figure 162: 57m/s incident wind speed

Figure 163: 57m/s incident wind speed PSD

Figure 164: Secondary rotor speed at 57m/s incident wind speed

Figure 165: Secondary rotor speed PSD at 57m/s incident wind speed

Figure 166: Secondary rotor torque at 57m/s incident wind speed

Figure 167: Secondary rotor torque PSD at 57m/s incident wind speed

Figure 168: Secondary rotor thrust at 57m/s incident wind speed

Figure 169: Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 57m/s incident wind speed

Figure 170: Secondary rotors combined power at 57m/s incident wind speed

Figure 171: Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 57m/s incident wind speed

Figure 172: Secondary rotors combined thrust at 57m/s incident wind speed

Figure 173: Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 57m/s incident wind speed

4 Above Rated Operation

4.1 Mode 4

4.1.1 wind speed = 14m/s, incident wind speed = 60m/s

List of figures in 4.1.1

174	Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 14m/s wind speed	47
175	14m/s wind speed	47
176	14m/s wind speed PSD	47
177	Primary rotor speed at 14m/s wind speed	48
178	Primary rotor speed PSD at 14m/s wind speed	48
179	Primary rotor torque at 14m/s wind speed	48
180	Primary rotor torque PSD at 14m/s wind speed	48
181	Primary rotor power at 14m/s wind speed	48
182	Primary rotor power PSD at 14m/s wind speed	48
183	Primary rotor pitch angle at 14m/s wind speed	49
184	Primary rotor pitch angle PSD at 14m/s wind speed	49
185	Upper blade in-plane RBM at 14m/s wind speed.....	49
186	Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 14m/s wind speed.....	49
187	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 14m/s wind speed	49
188	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 14m/s wind speed	49
189	Lower blade in-plane RBM at 14m/s wind speed.....	50
190	Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 14m/s wind speed.....	50
191	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 14m/s wind speed.....	50
192	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 14m/s wind speed.....	50
193	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 14m/s wind speed	50
194	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 14m/s wind speed	50
195	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 14m/s wind speed.....	51
196	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 14m/s wind speed.....	51
197	Variation of secondary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 60m/s wind speed (14m/s ambient wind speed)	51
198	60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s).....	51
199	60m/s incident wind speed PSD (14m/s).....	51
200	Secondary rotor speed at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)	52

201 Secondary rotor speed PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s) 52

202 Secondary rotor torque at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s) 52

203 Secondary rotor torque PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)..... 52

204 Secondary rotor thrust at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s) 52

205 Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s) 52

206 Secondary rotors combined power at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s) 53

207 Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s) 53

208 Secondary rotors combined thrust at 14m/s incident wind speed (14m/s) 53

209 Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s) 53

Figure 174: Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 175: 14m/s wind speed

Figure 176: 14m/s wind speed PSD

Figure 177: Primary rotor speed at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 178: Primary rotor speed PSD at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 179: Primary rotor torque at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 180: Primary rotor torque PSD at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 181: Primary rotor power at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 182: Primary rotor power PSD at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 183: Primary rotor pitch angle at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 184: Primary rotor pitch angle PSD at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 185: Upper blade in-plane RBM at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 186: Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 187: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 188: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 189: Lower blade in-plane RBM at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 190: Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 191: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 192: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 193: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 194: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 195: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 196: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 14m/s wind speed

Figure 197: Variation of secondary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 60m/s wind speed (14m/s ambient wind speed)

Figure 198: 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

Figure 199: 60m/s incident wind speed PSD (14m/s)

Figure 200: Secondary rotor speed at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

Figure 201: Secondary rotor speed PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

Figure 202: Secondary rotor torque at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

Figure 203: Secondary rotor torque PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

Figure 204: Secondary rotor thrust at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

Figure 205: Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

Figure 206: Secondary rotors combined power at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

Figure 207: Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

Figure 208: Secondary rotors combined thrust at 14m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

Figure 209: Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (14m/s)

4.1.2 wind speed = 17m/s, incident wind speed = 60m/s

List of figures in 4.1.2

210	Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 17m/s wind speed	55
211	17m/s wind speed	55
212	17m/s wind speed PSD	55
213	Primary rotor speed at 17m/s wind speed	56
214	Primary rotor speed PSD at 17m/s wind speed	56
215	Primary rotor torque at 17m/s wind speed	56
216	Primary rotor torque PSD at 17m/s wind speed	56
217	Primary rotor power at 17m/s wind speed	56
218	Primary rotor power PSD at 17m/s wind speed	56
219	Primary rotor pitch angle at 17m/s wind speed	57
220	Primary rotor pitch angle PSD at 17m/s wind speed	57
221	Upper blade in-plane RBM at 17m/s wind speed.....	57
222	Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 17m/s wind speed.....	57
223	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 17m/s wind speed	57
224	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 17m/s wind speed	57
225	Lower blade in-plane RBM at 17m/s wind speed.....	58
226	Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 17m/s wind speed.....	58
227	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 17m/s wind speed.....	58
228	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 17m/s wind speed.....	58
229	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 17m/s wind speed	58
230	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 17m/s wind speed	58
231	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 17m/s wind speed.....	59
232	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 17m/s wind speed.....	59
233	Variation of secondary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 60m/s wind speed (17m/s ambient wind speed)	59
234	60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s).....	59
235	60m/s incident wind speed PSD (17m/s).....	59
236	Secondary rotor speed at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)	60
237	Secondary rotor speed PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)	60
238	Secondary rotor torque at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s).....	60
239	Secondary rotor torque PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s).....	60

240 Secondary rotor thrust at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s) 60

241 Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s) 60

242 Secondary rotors combined power at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s) 61

243 Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s) 61

244 Secondary rotors combined thrust at 17m/s incident wind speed (17m/s) 61

245 Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s) 61

Figure 210: Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 211: 17m/s wind speed

Figure 212: 17m/s wind speed PSD

Figure 213: Primary rotor speed at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 214: Primary rotor speed PSD at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 215: Primary rotor torque at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 216: Primary rotor torque PSD at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 217: Primary rotor power at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 218: Primary rotor power PSD at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 219: Primary rotor pitch angle at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 220: Primary rotor pitch angle PSD at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 221: Upper blade in-plane RBM at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 222: Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 223: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 224: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 225: Lower blade in-plane RBM at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 226: Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 227: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 228: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 229: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 230: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 231: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 232: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 17m/s wind speed

Figure 233: Variation of secondary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 60m/s wind speed (17m/s ambient wind speed)

Figure 234: 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

Figure 235: 60m/s incident wind speed PSD (17m/s)

Figure 236: Secondary rotor speed at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

Figure 237: Secondary rotor speed PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

Figure 238: Secondary rotor torque at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

Figure 239: Secondary rotor torque PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

Figure 240: Secondary rotor thrust at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

Figure 241: Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

Figure 242: Secondary rotors combined power at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

Figure 243: Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

Figure 244: Secondary rotors combined thrust at 17m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

Figure 245: Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (17m/s)

4.2 Mode 5

4.2.1 wind speed = 20m/s, incident wind speed = 60m/s

List of figures in 4.2.1

246	Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 20m/s wind speed	63
247	20m/s wind speed	63
248	20m/s wind speed PSD	63
249	Primary rotor speed at 20m/s wind speed	64
250	Primary rotor speed PSD at 20m/s wind speed	64
251	Primary rotor torque at 20m/s wind speed	64
252	Primary rotor torque PSD at 20m/s wind speed	64
253	Primary rotor power at 20m/s wind speed	64
254	Primary rotor power PSD at 20m/s wind speed	64
255	Primary rotor pitch angle at 20m/s wind speed	65
256	Primary rotor pitch angle PSD at 20m/s wind speed	65
257	Upper blade in-plane RBM at 20m/s wind speed.....	65
258	Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 20m/s wind speed.....	65
259	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 20m/s wind speed	65
260	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 20m/s wind speed	65
261	Lower blade in-plane RBM at 20m/s wind speed.....	66
262	Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 20m/s wind speed.....	66
263	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 20m/s wind speed.....	66
264	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 20m/s wind speed.....	66
265	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 20m/s wind speed	66
266	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 20m/s wind speed	66
267	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 20m/s wind speed.....	67
268	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 20m/s wind speed.....	67
269	Variation of secondary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 60m/s wind speed (20m/s ambient wind speed)	67
270	60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)	67
271	60m/s incident wind speed PSD (20m/s)	67
272	Secondary rotor speed at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)	68
273	Secondary rotor speed PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)	68
274	Secondary rotor torque at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)	68

275 Secondary rotor torque PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s) 68

276 Secondary rotor thrust at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s) 68

277 Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s) 68

278 Secondary rotors combined power at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s) 69

279 Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s) 69

280 Secondary rotors combined thrust at 20m/s incident wind speed (20m/s) 69

281 Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s) 69

Figure 246: Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 247: 20m/s wind speed

Figure 248: 20m/s wind speed PSD

Figure 249: Primary rotor speed at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 250: Primary rotor speed PSD at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 251: Primary rotor torque at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 252: Primary rotor torque PSD at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 253: Primary rotor power at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 254: Primary rotor power PSD at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 255: Primary rotor pitch angle at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 256: Primary rotor pitch angle PSD at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 257: Upper blade in-plane RBM at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 258: Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 259: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 260: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 261: Lower blade in-plane RBM at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 262: Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 263: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 264: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 265: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 266: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 267: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 268: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 20m/s wind speed

Figure 269: Variation of secondary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 60m/s wind speed (20m/s ambient wind speed)

Figure 270: 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

Figure 271: 60m/s incident wind speed PSD (20m/s)

Figure 272: Secondary rotor speed at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

Figure 273: Secondary rotor speed PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

Figure 274: Secondary rotor torque at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

Figure 275: Secondary rotor torque PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

Figure 276: Secondary rotor thrust at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

Figure 277: Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

Figure 278: Secondary rotors combined power at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

Figure 279: Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

Figure 280: Secondary rotors combined thrust at 20m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

Figure 281: Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (20m/s)

4.2.2 wind speed = 23m/s, incident wind speed = 60m/s

List of figures in 4.2.2

282	Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 23m/s wind speed	71
283	23m/s wind speed	71
284	23m/s wind speed PSD	71
285	Primary rotor speed at 23m/s wind speed	72
286	Primary rotor speed PSD at 23m/s wind speed	72
287	Primary rotor torque at 23m/s wind speed	72
288	Primary rotor torque PSD at 23m/s wind speed	72
289	Primary rotor power at 23m/s wind speed	72
290	Primary rotor power PSD at 23m/s wind speed	72
291	Primary rotor pitch angle at 23m/s wind speed	73
292	Primary rotor pitch angle PSD at 23m/s wind speed	73
293	Upper blade in-plane RBM at 23m/s wind speed.....	73
294	Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 23m/s wind speed.....	73
295	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 23m/s wind speed	73
296	Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 23m/s wind speed	73
297	Lower blade in-plane RBM at 23m/s wind speed.....	74
298	Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 23m/s wind speed.....	74
299	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 23m/s wind speed.....	74
300	Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 23m/s wind speed.....	74
301	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 23m/s wind speed	74
302	Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 23m/s wind speed	74
303	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 23m/s wind speed.....	75
304	Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 23m/s wind speed.....	75
305	Variation of secondary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 60m/s wind speed (23m/s ambient wind speed)	75
306	60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)	75
307	60m/s incident wind speed PSD (23m/s)	75
308	Secondary rotor speed at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)	76
309	Secondary rotor speed PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)	76
310	Secondary rotor torque at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)	76
311	Secondary rotor torque PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s).....	76

312 Secondary rotor thrust at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s) 76

313 Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s) 76

314 Secondary rotors combined power at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s) 77

315 Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s) 77

316 Secondary rotors combined thrust at 23m/s incident wind speed (23m/s) 77

317 Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s) 77

Figure 282: Primary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 283: 23m/s wind speed

Figure 284: 23m/s wind speed PSD

Figure 285: Primary rotor speed at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 286: Primary rotor speed PSD at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 287: Primary rotor torque at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 288: Primary rotor torque PSD at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 289: Primary rotor power at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 290: Primary rotor power PSD at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 291: Primary rotor pitch angle at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 292: Primary rotor pitch angle PSD at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 293: Upper blade in-plane RBM at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 294: Upper blade in-plane RBM PSD at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 295: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 296: Upper blade out-of-plane RBM PSD at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 297: Lower blade in-plane RBM at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 298: Lower blade in-plane RBM PSD at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 299: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 300: Upper blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 301: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 302: Upper blade out-of-plane angular displacement PSD at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 303: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 304: Lower blade in-plane angular displacement PSD at 23m/s wind speed

Figure 305: Variation of secondary rotor torque vs rotor speed at 60m/s wind speed (23m/s ambient wind speed)

Figure 306: 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

Figure 307: 60m/s incident wind speed PSD (23m/s)

Figure 308: Secondary rotor speed at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

Figure 309: Secondary rotor speed PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

Figure 310: Secondary rotor torque at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

Figure 311: Secondary rotor torque PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

Figure 312: Secondary rotor thrust at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

Figure 313: Secondary rotor thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

Figure 314: Secondary rotors combined power at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

Figure 315: Secondary rotors combined power PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

Figure 316: Secondary rotors combined thrust at 23m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

Figure 317: Secondary rotors combined thrust PSD at 60m/s incident wind speed (23m/s)

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